

Isolation and characterization of lytic *Escherichia coli* phages from Al-Zarqa River and evaluation of their in vitro antibiofilm activity

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Received 12 February 2026 ♦ Accepted 7 April 2026 ♦ Published 5 May 2026

Citation: Al Tall Y, Al-qasem A, Alshraiedeh N, Alsaggar M (2026) Isolation and characterization of lytic *Escherichia coli* phages from Al-Zarqa River and evaluation of their in vitro antibiofilm activity. Pharmacia 73: e188523. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e188523>

Abstract

The increasing prevalence of antibiotic-resistant *Escherichia coli* and its ability to form biofilms necessitate alternative antimicrobial strategies. In this study, two lytic bacteriophages infecting *E. coli* were isolated from freshwater samples collected from the Al-Zarqa River in Jordan and characterized phenotypically. Transmission electron microscopy identified both phages as tailed viruses within the order *Caudovirales*, provisionally classified as *Podoviridae*-like and *Myoviridae*-like phages. Both phages exhibited efficient lytic activity against the reference host strain, with latent periods of 20–30 min and burst sizes of 5–9 plaque-forming units per infected cell. The phages remained stable across a wide range of temperatures and *pH* values, retaining infectivity during storage at 4 °C. Host-range analysis demonstrated narrow strain specificity. Both phages significantly inhibited biofilm formation and reduced established biofilms in a dose-dependent manner. These results support the potential of the isolated phages as promising antibiofilm agents for further development.

Keywords

Antibiofilm agents, biofilm inhibition, *Caudovirales*, freshwater isolate, lytic bacteriophages, phage therapy

Introduction

Infectious diseases continue to pose a serious threat to public health and global economic stability (Qu et al. 2025). Throughout history, they have ranked among the leading causes of mortality and disability, and in the 21st century, this threat has intensified due to the emergence and re-emergence of novel pathogens (Bloom and Cadarette 2019; De Gaetano et al. 2025). Over the past three decades, at least 30 new infectious agents affecting humans have been identified, most of which are zoonotic in origin and influenced by socioeconomic, ecological, and environmental factors

(Nii-Trebi 2017; Carlson et al. 2022). These conditions have increased human exposure to infectious agents, underscoring the need for effective and adaptable strategies to combat infectious disease threats (Ortiz-Millan 2025).

The advent of antibiotics in the 20th century revolutionized modern medicine, drastically reducing mortality from bacterial infections (Hutchings et al. 2019). However, the widespread and often inappropriate use of antibiotics has led to the global crisis of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) (Estany-Gestal et al. 2024). Bacteria can develop resistance through spontaneous mutations or by acquiring resistance genes from other organisms (Ghosh et al. 2019). Resistant

organisms are now found in humans, animals, food, water, and the environment, making AMR a universal challenge (Sharma et al. 2024). Of particular concern are multi-drug-resistant (MDR), extensively drug-resistant (XDR), and pan-drug-resistant (PDR) bacterial strains, which severely limit treatment options (Tacconelli et al. 2018). MDR is defined as non-susceptibility to at least one agent in three or more antimicrobial categories, XDR as non-susceptibility to at least one agent in all but two or fewer categories, and PDR as non-susceptibility to all agents in all antimicrobial categories tested (Magiorakos et al. 2012). The World Health Organization (WHO) ranks antimicrobial resistance among the top global health threats, with recent estimates highlighting its increasing burden and projected impact if left unaddressed (Estany-Gestal et al. 2024).

The growing ineffectiveness of current antibiotics underscores the urgent need for novel antibacterial strategies and alternative therapeutic options. Among these, bacteriophage therapy has regained attention as a promising solution to combat resistant infections (Gordillo Altamirano and Barr 2019). Bacteriophages are viruses that infect bacteria and can follow either a lytic or lysogenic lifecycle, with only lytic phages causing immediate bacterial cell lysis (Kortright et al. 2019; Shang et al. 2025). They can be readily isolated from natural sources, such as sewage and rivers, especially in regions with high bacterial loads (Nale and Clokie 2021). Phages are highly specific, self-amplifying, relatively inexpensive to isolate, and can be formulated in multiple delivery formats, including liquids, creams, and solid supports (Olawade et al. 2024). Their ability to target biofilm-forming bacteria is particularly relevant, given that biofilms contribute to chronic and recalcitrant infections (Mayorga-Ramos et al. 2024).

In this study, the aim was to isolate and characterize bacteriophages from the Al-Zarqa River in Jordan with lytic activity against *Escherichia coli*, a clinically significant pathogen known for its AMR potential and biofilm-forming capacity (Ramatla et al. 2023). The morphology, lytic activity, growth characteristics, environmental stability, host range, biofilm-disrupting capabilities, and long-term storage stability of the isolated phages were investigated to assess their therapeutic potential.

Materials and methods

Bacterial hosts

Four reference strains obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC) were used in this study: *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922), *E. coli* (ATCC BAA-2452), *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 29213), and *S. aureus* (ATCC BAA-44). All bacterial strains were cultured in 8 mL of Luria-Bertani (LB) broth at 37 °C with shaking at 110 rpm for 3–4 h to reach the logarithmic growth phase. Each batch included parallel subcultures of the inoculum on LB agar plates and media controls, followed by 48-hour incubation at 37 °C to confirm the purity of the bacterial cultures and sterility of the media.

Sample collection

Surface water samples were collected from the Al-Zarqa River (ZR) at Jerash Bridge (Jordan) using sterile 500 mL polypropylene containers. The precise GPS location of the collection site was recorded (32°13'03.7"N, 35°52'54.1"E). Samples were transported to the laboratory within 2 h of collection in a cooled container and stored at 4 °C until processing.

Sample processing

The water samples were centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 min to remove particulate matter. The resulting supernatant was sequentially filtered through 0.45 µm and 0.2 µm pore-size syringe filters (ExtraGene, USA). The filtered water was aliquoted and stored at 4 °C for subsequent phage enrichment and isolation procedures (Clokie and Kropinski 2009).

Phage enrichment, isolation, and purification

Filtered river water was first obtained to ensure the removal of bacterial cells and subsequently mixed with an equal volume of double-strength LB broth supplemented with 10 mM MgSO₄ and 5 mM CaCl₂ (Clokie and Kropinski 2009). Each bacterial host strain was added separately to individual aliquots of the enrichment mixture prior to incubation to allow phage propagation.

The enriched mixture was incubated with partially unscrewed caps on a shaker at 110 rpm for 24 h at 37 °C. After incubation, the culture was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm (~12,062 × g) for 10 min at 4 °C using a JA-10 fixed-angle rotor (k-factor = 2,720) to pellet bacterial cells and debris. The resulting supernatants were passed through sterile 0.22 µm pore-size syringe filters (ExtraGene, USA) to obtain cell-free phage-containing filtrates. To confirm the absence of viable bacterial cells, 1 mL of each filtrate was plated onto LB agar and incubated at 37 °C for 48 h. Only sterile filtrates (i.e., showing no bacterial growth) were used for downstream assays.

The presence of phages in the filtrates was assessed using a modified double-agar overlay (DAO) method (Clokie and Kropinski 2009). Briefly, 200 µL of log-phase host culture (OD₆₀₀ ≈ 0.3) was mixed with 200 µL of phage-containing filtrate and incubated for 20 min at 37 °C to allow phage adsorption. The mixture was then combined with 4 mL of molten 0.6% LB soft agar (cooled to ~45 °C) and poured onto solidified LB agar plates (90 mm diameter). Plates were left at room temperature for 10 min to solidify and then incubated overnight at 37 °C in an inverted position. Plaque formation on the bacterial lawn was interpreted as evidence of lytic phage activity. Plaque diameters were measured using a sterile ruler across a minimum of 10 distinct plaques, and morphology (e.g., clear, turbid, halo presence) was recorded visually.

Eleven purification cycles were performed to isolate phages with distinct plaque morphologies. Individual plaques were carefully picked using a sterile flame-sterilized needle and transferred into 1–2 mL of sterile saline magnesium gelatin buffer (SMG), which is composed of 50 mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.5), 100 mM NaCl, 10 mM MgSO₄, and 0.01% gelatin. The resulting phage suspensions were filtered through sterile 0.22 µm syringe filters (ExtraGene, USA), serially diluted, and retested for lytic activity using the DAO method as described above.

For each host used in the purification process, a bacterial control plate was prepared by mixing 200 µL of bacterial suspension with approximately 4 mL of molten soft LB agar

$$\text{Phage concentration} \left(\frac{\text{PFU}}{\text{mL}} \right) = \text{Number of plaques} \times 2.5 \times \text{Dilution factor}$$

Transmission electron microscopy

Phage filtrates were purified and prepared for transmission electron microscopy (TEM) using a negative staining protocol adapted from Clokie and Kropinski (2009), with full parameters specified to ensure reproducibility. High-titer phage suspensions (~10⁹ PFU/mL) were centrifuged at 25,000 × g for 60 min at 4 °C using a Sigma 3K30 centrifuge (Sigma Laborzentrifugen GmbH, Osterode am Harz, Germany) equipped with a high-speed fixed-angle rotor (Model 12150). The resulting pellets were gently resuspended and washed once with 0.1 M ammonium acetate buffer (pH 7.0) to remove residual salts.

A 10 µL aliquot of each purified phage suspension was placed onto a Formvar-coated, carbon-stabilized copper grid (200 mesh size; Electron Microscopy Sciences, USA) and incubated for 2 min at room temperature. Excess liquid was wicked off with filter paper, and the grids were immediately stained with 2% (w/v) uranyl acetate (pH 4.5) for 60 s. After gentle air-drying, the grids were examined using a Morgagni 268 TEM (FEI, Eindhoven, Netherlands) operated at 60 kV. Images were captured using iTEM software, and particle dimensions were measured directly from the instrument's calibrated internal scale bar.

Phage stock preparation and titer

Two purified phages, vB_EcoP_ZR1 and vB_EcoM_ZR2, were propagated from the final purified filtrates. The standard protocol was followed based on established methods for high-titer stock preparation (Green and Sambrook 2012). Log-phase cultures of the corresponding bacterial hosts (OD₆₀₀ ≈ 0.4–0.6) were diluted and mixed with each phage filtrate at a multiplicity of infection (MOI) of 9. The mixtures were incubated for 20 min at 37 °C to allow efficient phage adsorption.

Following adsorption, 50 mL of pre-warmed LB broth was added to each phage–bacteria mixture, and the cultures were incubated overnight (16–18 h) at 37 °C with shaking at 140 rpm. After incubation, cultures were centrifuged at 10,000 rpm (~12,062 × g) for 10 min at 4 °C using a Beckman J2 21 centrifuge

(0.6%). These control plates were incubated at 37 °C for 48 h during each purification cycle to confirm the viability of the bacterial host and the absence of contamination.

The titers of the purified phage filtrates were determined by averaging three independent plaque counts and expressed as plaque-forming units per milliliter (PFU/mL). For each dilution, the phage concentration was calculated by multiplying the number of plaques by the dilution factor (DF) and the volume correction factor (VCF). Since the total plated volume in each assay was standardized to 400 µL (0.4 mL), the VCF was calculated as 1/0.4, yielding a value of 2.5. The final equation used for determining phage concentration was:

(Palo Alto, CA, USA) equipped with a JA-10 fixed-angle rotor (k-factor = 2,720) to pellet bacterial debris. The resulting supernatants were collected and filtered through 0.22 µm pore-size syringe filters (ExtraGene, USA). To confirm sterility and procedural consistency, two control flasks were included: one containing 40 mL of LB broth inoculated with bacterial cells only and one containing sterile LB medium alone.

The phage titers of the resulting lysates were determined using the DAO method and serial dilutions, as described previously. Final titers were obtained by averaging three independent measurements and expressed as PFU/mL.

The effect of pH and temperature on phage stability

The heat and pH stability of the two phage stocks, vB_EcoP_ZR1 and vB_EcoM_ZR2, were evaluated using standard protocols (Adnan et al. 2020; Abdelsattar et al. 2021).

To assess thermal stability, 100 µL of each phage stock (initial titer ~10⁷ PFU/mL) was added to 900 µL of LB broth (pH 7.4) and incubated at various temperatures (37 °C, 45 °C, 55 °C, 65 °C, 70 °C, and 80 °C) for 1 h. After incubation, the remaining phage titers were determined using the double-agar overlay (DAO) method at appropriate serial dilutions. Each condition was tested in triplicate, and the mean of the independent measurements was reported.

To assess pH stability, 1 mL of each phage (initial titer ~10⁷ PFU/mL) was mixed with 9 mL of LB broth adjusted to different pH values (3, 5, 7, 9, and 11) using 1 M HCl or NaOH. The phage suspensions were incubated at 37 °C for 15 h. After incubation, phage titers were determined using the DAO method. Each condition was tested in triplicate.

One-step growth curve

The one-step growth curve of each phage was determined using a standardized protocol with minor modifications (Atlas 2010). Briefly, a culture of the host bacterium *E. coli* (ATCC 25922) was grown to the logarithmic phase in LB broth. The culture was then infected with phage vB_

EcoP_ZR1 and vB_EcoM_ZR2 at MOIs of 0.05 and 0.06, respectively. The mixtures were incubated at 37 °C while shaking at 120 rpm.

After 5 min of adsorption, the phage–bacteria mixtures were diluted 10^{-4} in pre-warmed LB broth to prevent further infection. Samples (100 µL) were taken at regular time intervals (5, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 65, and 80 min), and phage titers were determined by the DAO method. The 5-min time point was designated as Time Zero (T_0), representing the titer of the remaining unadsorbed extracellular phages and the beginning of the growth cycle.

The resulting data were used to construct the phage one-step growth curve. The latent period—defined as the time between phage adsorption and the beginning of host cell lysis—was identified from the curve. The burst size, representing the number of new phage particles released per infected bacterial cell, was calculated by dividing the maximum PFU/mL obtained during the burst phase by the PFU/mL at Time Zero (T_0). To ensure accuracy, the experiment was conducted in triplicate, and the mean values were reported.

Susceptibility of clinical isolates to phages

Screening clinical isolates' susceptibility to phages

To evaluate the ability of phages to infect diverse *E. coli* strains, four animal-derived clinical isolates were screened for susceptibility using the spot assay, as previously described (Khan Mirzaei and Nilsson 2015). Briefly, 4 mL of molten 0.6% LB soft agar was mixed with 100 µL of a log-phase bacterial culture, vortexed, and immediately poured onto a pre-warmed LB agar plate. Plates were allowed to solidify at room temperature for 15 min.

After solidification, 10 µL aliquots of each phage dilution (10^7 , 10^5 , 10^4 , and 10^3 PFU/mL) were spotted onto the bacterial lawn. The plates were left to air-dry for 20 min and then incubated overnight at 37 °C. For quality control, each run included the original host strain used for phage isolation to verify phage viability. To rule out false zones of clearance due to broth diffusion, 10 µL of sterile LB broth was also spotted as a negative control.

Each clinical isolate was tested in triplicate. To confirm the purity of bacterial suspensions, subcultures of the inoculum were plated on LB agar prior to use. Media sterility was confirmed by incubating uninoculated broth and agar at 37 °C for 48 h.

A grading system was applied to classify the susceptibility of clinical *E. coli* isolates based on their response to the phage spot assay (Table 1). Lytic responses were assigned numerical grades reflecting the presence and clarity of lytic zones or plaque formation. Isolates exhibiting ambiguous lysis patterns were confirmed using the DAO assay. Control spots containing LB broth were included to exclude diffusion-related artifacts.

Table 1. Grading system used to interpret spot assay results for clinical *Escherichia coli* isolates.

Grade	Observed lytic effect in spot assay	Interpretation
0	No lytic zone observed	Non-susceptible
1	Distinct plaques observed	Susceptible
1F	Faint or hazy lytic zone without plaque formation	Possibly susceptible (requires confirmation)
1C	Clear lytic zone observed without plaque formation	Possibly susceptible (requires confirmation)

Plating clinical isolates for confirmation

To rule out false-positive lysis caused by residual free lysins in the phage filtrate (“lysis from without”), *E. coli* isolates that showed lytic zones on the spot assay but failed to produce plaques at the lowest phage concentration were re-examined with the DAO method. Briefly, 400 µL of appropriately diluted phage filtrate was mixed with 400 µL of the clinical isolate requiring confirmation, and the mixture was incubated for 20 min at 37 °C to allow adsorption. The mixture was then combined with ~4 mL of molten 0.6% LB soft agar, vortexed gently, and immediately poured onto an LB agar base plate. After 15 min of room-temperature solidification, plates were incubated overnight at 37 °C.

Isolates that yielded clearly defined plaques on the confluent bacterial lawn were classified as susceptible to the corresponding phage, whereas those showing no plaque formation were deemed resistant. The purity of all bacterial suspensions was verified at the time of preparation by subculturing the inoculum onto LB agar. Media sterility was confirmed by incubating uninoculated broth and agar plates at 37 °C for 48 h.

Antibiotic susceptibility of the phage-susceptible isolate

Drug susceptibility testing (DST) of the phage-susceptible *E. coli* isolates was performed using the disc diffusion method following the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute guidelines (Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute 2020). The results were used to classify the isolates as multidrug-resistant (MDR), extensively drug-resistant (XDR), or pandrug-resistant (PDR) based on internationally accepted definitions (Magiorakos et al. 2012).

This classification provided insight into the antibiotic resistance profiles of the phage-susceptible isolates.

Host range analysis

To determine the host range of the isolated phages, their lytic activity was tested against nine reference bacterial strains, comprising both Gram-positive and Gram-negative species. The tested strains included *E. coli* (NCTC 13476), *E. coli* (ATCC BAA-2452), *S. aureus* (ATCC 29213), *S. aureus* (ATCC BAA-44), *Listeria monocytogenes*

(ATCC 19115), *Lactobacillus gasseri* (ATCC 19992), *Enterococcus faecalis* (ATCC 29212), *Shigella flexneri* (ATCC 12022), and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (ATCC 700603).

The host range was assessed using a modified spot assay method (Clokic and Kropinski 2009). In brief, 100 μ L of each log-phase bacterial suspension was mixed with approximately 4 mL of molten 0.6% LB soft agar, vortexed gently, and poured onto LB agar base plates. The top agar was allowed to solidify at room temperature for 20 min. Then, 10 μ L of each phage stock (containing $\sim 10^6$ PFU of vB_EcoP_ZR1 and $\sim 10^8$ PFU of vB_EcoM_ZR2) was spotted onto the surface of the solidified agar.

The primary *E. coli* host strain used for phage isolation was included as a positive control to confirm phage viability. In addition, 10 μ L of sterile LB broth was spotted on each plate as a negative control to exclude false clearance due to broth diffusion.

Each reference strain was tested in triplicate to ensure reproducibility. The impact of each phage on the tested strains was scored using the previously described grading system (Table 1). Strains that exhibited lytic zones without plaque formation were subsequently retested using the double-agar overlay (DAO) method to confirm their susceptibility.

To ensure the purity of all bacterial suspensions, subcultures were plated on LB agar using the same inoculum employed for broth cultures. Media sterility was confirmed by incubating uninoculated broth and agar at 37 °C for 48 h.

Biofilm formation assay

The *E. coli* (ATCC 25922) strain was cultured in LB broth to the logarithmic phase and adjusted to 1×10^7 CFU/mL. Bacterial suspensions were then mixed with equal volumes of phage suspensions at different multiplicities of infection (MOI): one and 0.1 for vB_EcoP_ZR1 and one and 0.01 for vB_EcoM_ZR2. A total volume of 200 μ L of each mixture was dispensed into individual wells of a 96-well microtiter plate fitted with peg lids (Nunc-TSP, Thermo Fisher Scientific). Each treatment was performed in octuplicate ($n = 8$); wells containing *E. coli* without phages served as untreated biofilm controls.

The plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h with shaking at 120 rpm. After incubation, the pegs were gently rinsed three times with 200 μ L of sterile phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) to remove planktonic (free-floating) cells. Pegs were then transferred into new microplates containing 145 μ L of fresh PBS per well, ensuring full submersion of the biofilms formed on the pegs.

To dislodge adherent biofilm cells, the plates were placed in an ultrasonic water bath (Elmasonic S30H, Elma Schmidbauer GmbH, Germany) and sonicated at 37 kHz for 30 min. The recovered biofilm suspensions were serially diluted and plated on LB agar. Plates were incubated overnight at 37 °C, and colony-forming units (CFUs) were counted the next day.

The number of viable biofilm-associated cells was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Number of viable cells} \left(\frac{\text{CFU}}{\text{mL}} \right) = \frac{\text{Number of colonies} \times \text{Dilution Factor}}{\text{Volume of sample (mL)}}$$

Biofilm clearance assay

E. coli (ATCC 25922) was cultured in LB broth to the logarithmic phase and adjusted to a final concentration of $\sim 1 \times 10^7$ CFU/mL. A total of 200 μ L of this bacterial suspension was added to each well of a 96-well microtiter plate fitted with peg lids (Nunc-TSP, Thermo Fisher Scientific). To allow biofilm development, the plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h with shaking at 120 rpm. Following incubation, the pegs were transferred into fresh microtiter plates containing 200 μ L of phage suspension (10^8 PFU/well). Wells containing established biofilms but no phage were included as untreated controls. The plates were then incubated at 37 °C with shaking at 120 rpm for an additional 24 h to allow phage-mediated biofilm disruption. After treatment, the pegs were rinsed three times with 200 μ L of sterile PBS to remove non-adherent cells, then transferred into new microtiter plates containing 145 μ L of PBS per well to cover the residual biofilms. To dislodge adherent cells, plates were sonicated in an ultrasonic water bath (Elmasonic S30H, Elma Schmidbauer GmbH, Germany) at 37 kHz for 30 min.

The resulting suspensions were serially diluted, plated on LB agar, and incubated overnight at 37 °C. CFUs were enumerated the following day.

The percentage of biofilm remaining was calculated by dividing the number of viable cells in phage-treated wells by the number in untreated control wells, multiplied by 100. Biofilm clearance was then expressed as the difference between 100% and the remaining biofilm percentage.

Long-term phage stock stability

The long-term stability of phage stocks was evaluated under four different storage conditions:

1. At room temperature (RT, ~ 22 – 25 °C).
2. Refrigeration at 4 °C.
3. Freezing at -20 °C in 12.5% glycerol (v/v).
4. Deep freezing at -60 °C in 50% glycerol (v/v).

Aliquots of freshly prepared, high-titer phage filtrates ($\sim 10^9$ PFU/mL) were stored under the above conditions in sterile microcentrifuge tubes. Samples were withdrawn at one-week intervals for the first four weeks and subsequently at weeks 6, 8, and 10.

Phage viability at each time point was assessed using the DAO assay as described earlier. Serial dilutions of the phage suspensions were prepared in SMG buffer, and plaques in countable dilution plates (20–200 plaques)

were enumerated. For each condition and time point, the mean of three biological replicates ($n = 3$) was calculated and presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD).

To ensure assay integrity, the bacterial host purity was confirmed by subculturing each inoculum on LB agar and verifying colony morphology. Additionally, media sterility was confirmed by incubating uninoculated LB broth and LB agar plates at 37 °C for 48 h and observing for any microbial growth.

Results

Phage isolation

Bacteriophages were successfully isolated from Al-Zarqa River water samples using *S. aureus* (ATCC 29213) and *E. coli* (ATCC 25922) as bacterial hosts, as indicated by plaque formation on DAO plates. However, the *Staphylococcus*-specific phages exhibited notable instability and poor viability, as their plaques disappeared rapidly following initial detection. When stored phage stocks were later retested using the DAO method, no plaques were observed, confirming a complete loss of infectivity and making further characterization unfeasible.

In contrast, the *E. coli*-specific phages remained stable, consistently produced plaques upon propagation, and were selected for further characterization and evaluation.

Phage plaque morphology

Two phages were successfully purified from the collected water sample, each exhibiting distinct plaque morphologies. These phages were designated *E. coli* phage vB_EcoP_ZR1 and *E. coli* phage vB_EcoM_ZR2, and their plaques were differentiated on bacterial lawns of the primary host, *E. coli* (ATCC 25922) (Fig. 1): phage vB_EcoP_ZR1 produced round, clear plaques with irregular edges and no surrounding halo. In contrast, vB_EcoM_ZR2 generated plaques that were uniformly clear, round, and well-defined, with a prominent halo zone surrounding each plaque. These plaques measured 1.0–2.0 mm in diameter.

Transmission electron microscopy

TEM analysis revealed that both bacteriophages exhibited morphology consistent with the order *Caudovirales* (tailed bacteriophages). The morphological features of vB_EcoP_ZR1 (Fig. 2) were consistent with *Podoviridae*-like morphology, characterized by short, non-contractile tails (Ackermann 2003). The phage exhibited a hexagonal head structure consistent with icosahedral symmetry, with average head dimensions of 95 \times 112 nm, and a short, non-contractile tail measuring approximately 16 nm.

In contrast, vB_EcoM_ZR2 exhibited *Myoviridae*-like morphology based on TEM observations (Fig. 3). Phages of this family are distinguished by their long, contractile tails (Ackermann 2003). vB_EcoM_ZR2 had a hexagonal

Figure 1. Plaque morphology of *Escherichia coli* phages on double-agar overlay plates. **A.** vB_EcoP_ZR1 formed round, clear plaques with irregular margins and no surrounding halo; **B.** vB_EcoM_ZR2 produced clear, round plaques with well-defined edges and a distinct halo. Phages were plated on lawns of *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922).

Figure 2. Transmission electron microscopy images of *Escherichia coli* phage vB_EcoP_ZR1, negatively stained with uranyl acetate. **A.** Representative virion showing an icosahedral capsid; **B.** Enlarged view highlighting the short, non-contractile tail, consistent with *Podoviridae*-like morphology.

Figure 3. Transmission electron microscopy images of *Escherichia coli* phage vB_EcoM_ZR2, negatively stained with uranyl acetate. **A.** Icosahedral capsid morphology; **B.** Enlarged view of the virion, consistent with *Myoviridae*-like morphology.

head with slightly elongated dimensions (68 \times 96 nm) and a long contractile tail measuring approximately 127 nm.

Phage stock titer

Infection of the primary host, *E. coli* (ATCC 25922), with each phage resulted in a high-titer lysate, with a multiplicity of infection (MOI) of approximately nine for both phages. Plaques were counted on plates with countable numbers, and phage concentrations were calculated by averaging values from three independent plates. The final titers of the prepared phage stocks were 6 \times 10⁸ PFU/mL for vB_EcoP_ZR1 and 5.5 \times 10⁹ PFU/mL for vB_EcoM_ZR2.

The effect of pH and temperature on phage stability

The thermal stability of the phages was assessed over a range of temperatures (Fig. 4A, B). Both phages exhibited similar thermal profiles. Incubation at 37 °C and 45 °C for 1 h had minimal impact on phage titers, which remained close to initial values. However, a noticeable decline in titer was observed at 55 °C, followed by a progressive reduction at 65 °C and 70 °C. At 80 °C, both phages experienced a ~2-log reduction in titer, indicating reduced thermal stability at higher temperatures.

The pH stability of the phages was also evaluated at 37 °C for 15 h. Both phages maintained considerable stability at pH 5, 7, 9, and 11, with only minor reductions in

titer. However, at pH 3, a marked decrease in phage activity was observed, with a 1.5-log reduction in titer for vB_EcoP_ZR1 (Fig. 4C) and a 4-log reduction for vB_EcoM_ZR2 (Fig. 4D).

One-step growth curve

The one-step growth curve analysis of phages vB_EcoP_ZR1 (Fig. 5) and vB_EcoM_ZR2 (Fig. 6) revealed a typical infection and replication pattern characteristic of lytic bacteriophages. The latent period was approximately 30 min for vB_EcoP_ZR1 and 20 min for vB_EcoM_ZR2. This was followed by a 35 min rise period for vB_EcoP_ZR1 and a 45 min rise period for vB_EcoM_ZR2, during which the phage population increased exponentially.

Figure 4. Thermal and pH stability profiles of phages vB_EcoP_ZR1 and vB_EcoM_ZR2. **A.** Thermal stability of phage vB_EcoP_ZR1 at different temperatures; **B.** Thermal stability of phage vB_EcoM_ZR2 at different temperatures; **C.** pH stability of phage vB_EcoP_ZR1 across a pH range of 3–11; **D.** pH stability of phage vB_EcoM_ZR2 across a pH range of 3–11. Phage titers were determined after a 1-hour incubation under the indicated conditions and are expressed as log₁₀ PFU/mL. Values represent the mean of three replicates ± standard deviation.

Figure 5. One-step growth curve of phage vB_EcoP_ZR1 at a multiplicity of infection of 0.05. Phage titers (PFU/mL) were determined at different time points following an infection with *Escherichia coli*.

Figure 6. One-step growth curve of phage vB_EcoM_ZR2 at a multiplicity of infection of 0.06. Phage titers (PFU/mL) were determined at different time points following an infection with *Escherichia coli*.

The complete replication cycle, from initial attachment to progeny phage release, was completed in approximately 65 min for both phages. The burst size, defined as the average number of phage particles released per infected bacterial cell, was estimated at five for vB_EcoP_ZR1 and nine for vB_EcoM_ZR2.

Susceptibility of clinical isolates to phages

The susceptibility of *E. coli* clinical isolates to the isolated phages was initially evaluated using the spot assay. Lytic activity was assessed based on plaque clarity and morphology and classified according to the grading system described in Table 1. The observed lytic patterns for each clinical isolate are summarized in Table 2.

To confirm productive infection, isolates exhibiting clear lytic activity in the spot assay were further examined using the double-agar overlay (DAO) assay. Plaque formation was observed only in isolates that showed clear lysis in the spot assay, confirming true susceptibility, whereas faint or hazy lytic zones did not result in plaque formation.

In the spot assay, one of the four *E. coli* clinical strains isolated from animals showed definite susceptibility to phage vB_EcoM_ZR2, as indicated by clear lysis. This isolate was confirmed by plaque formation in the DAO assay and is shown in Fig. 7. The remaining three isolates showed either clear or faint lytic zones in the spot assay but did not produce plaques in the DAO assay and were therefore classified as non-susceptible to vB_EcoM_ZR2.

In contrast, phage vB_EcoP_ZR1 exhibited higher strain-level specificity and did not productively infect any of the tested clinical isolates. Three strains showed only faint lytic zones without distinct plaque formation at the lowest phage concentrations in the spot assay. They were similarly confirmed as non-susceptible upon DAO assay testing with phage vB_EcoP_ZR1.

Antibiotic susceptibility of the phage-susceptible isolate

The antibiotic susceptibility profile of the phage-susceptible *E. coli* clinical isolate (MAC) revealed resistance to multiple antimicrobial classes, fulfilling the criteria for a multidrug-resistant (MDR) phenotype, defined as resis-

Figure 7. Representative spot assay result for a clinical *Escherichia coli* isolate (MAC) tested against phage vB_EcoM_ZR2. The isolate showed clear susceptibility, as indicated by distinct plaque formation even at the lowest tested concentration in this assay (10^4 PFU/spot).

tance to at least one agent in three or more antimicrobial categories (Table 3).

Specifically, the MAC isolate exhibited resistance to tetracyclines, phenicols, β -lactam/ β -lactamase inhibitor combinations, folate pathway inhibitors, and sulfonamides. Intermediate susceptibility was observed for ampicillin and streptomycin.

In contrast, the isolate remained susceptible to fluoroquinolones, carbapenems (including meropenem, doripenem, and imipenem), and most cephalosporins. Overall, this resistance profile reflects limited susceptibility across several antimicrobial classes.

Host range analysis

Both phages demonstrated strong specificity toward *E. coli*, with lytic activity observed only in the primary host strain, *E. coli* ATCC 25922, used for isolation, as summarized in Table 4. No lytic activity was observed against any of the other tested bacterial species in the spot assay, except for *Shigella flexneri* (ATCC 12022). A faint and hazy lytic zone was observed for vB_EcoP_ZR1 on *S. flexneri* lawns, indicating a possible weak interaction.

Table 2. Grading categories used to interpret spot assay results for clinical *Escherichia coli* isolates.

0	1	IF	1C
No lysis	Plaques	Hazy lysis	Clear lysis

Table 3. Antibiotic susceptibility profile of the phage-susceptible *Escherichia coli* clinical isolate (MAC).

Antibiotic	Activity
Ampicillin	Intermediate
Amoxicillin-clavulanate	Resistant
Azithromycin	Susceptible
Cefazolin	Susceptible
Cefepime	Susceptible
Cefotaxime	Susceptible
Ceftazidime	Susceptible
Chloramphenicol	Resistant
Ciprofloxacin	Susceptible
Doripenem	Susceptible
Doxycycline	Susceptible
Gentamicin	Susceptible
Imipenem	Susceptible
Kanamycin	Susceptible
Meropenem	Susceptible
Nalidixic acid	Susceptible
Piperacillin-tazobactam	Susceptible
Streptomycin	Intermediate
Tetracycline	Resistant
Trimethoprim	Resistant
Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole	Resistant

Table 4. Host range analysis of phages vB_EcoP_ZR1 and vB_EcoM_ZR2, determined by the spot assay.

Host	vB_EcoP_ZR1	vB_EcoM_ZR2
<i>Escherichia coli</i> ATCC 25922	1	1
<i>Escherichia coli</i> NCTC 13476	0	0
<i>Escherichia coli</i> ATCC BAA-2452	0	0
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ATCC 29213	0	0
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ATCC BAA-44	0	0
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> ATCC 19115	0	0
<i>Lactobacillus gasseri</i> ATCC 19992	0	0
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i> ATCC 29212	0	0
<i>Shigella flexneri</i> ATCC 12022	1F	0
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> ATCC 700603	0	0

Abbreviations: 0, no lytic activity; 1, clear plaques; 1F, faint/hazy lytic zone (requires confirmation).

Subsequent testing using the more stringent DAO assay did not confirm susceptibility of *S. flexneri* to vB_EcoP_ZR1. The absence of plaque formation indicated that the observed lytic zone in the spot assay did not correspond to productive infection.

Furthermore, neither *E. coli* (NCTC 13476) nor *E. coli* (ATCC BAA-2452) exhibited susceptibility to either phage. Together, these results demonstrate that both vB_EcoP_ZR1 and vB_EcoM_ZR2 exhibit a narrow host range and strong strain-level specificity for *E. coli*.

Biofilm formation assay

A significant reduction in viable biofilm-associated cells was observed following treatment with both phages, compared to the untreated control (Fig. 8). For both phages,

Figure 8. Effect of purified phages on the inhibition of biofilm formation by *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922). **A.** Biofilm formation in the presence of phage vB_EcoP_ZR1 at different multiplicities of infection; **B.** Biofilm formation in the presence of phage vB_EcoM_ZR2 at different multiplicities of infection. Data represent the mean of three independent experiments \pm standard deviation.

an inverse correlation between MOI and biofilm viability was noted, indicating that higher phage concentrations (MOI 1) were more effective in inhibiting biofilm formation than lower MOIs.

At MOI 1, vB_EcoM_ZR2 reduced the bacterial load from 10 to 5.65 log CFU/mL, representing a 4.35-log reduction. Similarly, vB_EcoP_ZR1 decreased the count to 5.92 log CFU/mL, corresponding to a 4.08-log reduction. These results suggest that vB_EcoM_ZR2 exerted a slightly stronger antibiofilm effect than vB_EcoP_ZR1 under identical conditions.

At lower MOIs, both phages still demonstrated measurable antibiofilm activity, though with reduced efficacy. vB_EcoM_ZR2 at MOI 0.01 achieved a 2.83-log reduction, while vB_EcoP_ZR1 at MOI 0.1 resulted in a 2.65-log reduction compared to the untreated control. Despite the diminished effect at suboptimal phage concentrations, both phages retained the ability to disrupt biofilm formation, highlighting their potential as antibiofilm agents even at lower doses.

Biofilm clearance assay

The ability of phages to reduce mature *E. coli* biofilms was assessed following treatment with a titer of 1.0×10^8 PFU/mL (Fig. 9). Both phages significantly reduced biofilm viability compared to the untreated control.

Figure 9. Biofilm clearance activity of purified phages against mature *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922) biofilms. Biofilms were formed in 96-well plates for 24 h and subsequently treated with phages at a titer of 1×10^8 PFU/mL. Phosphate-buffered saline-treated biofilms served as untreated controls. Data are presented as the mean number of viable cells expressed as \log_{10} CFU/mL from three independent experiments \pm standard deviation.

Phage vB_EcoM_ZR2 demonstrated a slightly greater effect, achieving a 24% reduction in viable biofilm-associated cells, while vB_EcoP_ZR1 achieved a 21% reduction. Although the difference between the two phages was relatively small, these results suggest that vB_EcoM_ZR2 may be marginally more effective at clearing established biofilms under the tested conditions.

Long-term phage stock stability

The long-term stability of both phages was assessed over a 10-week storage period under various conditions, including 4 °C, room temperature, -20 °C, and -60 °C.

At 4 °C, both vB_EcoP_ZR1 and vB_EcoM_ZR2 remained relatively stable throughout the 10 weeks, with an approximate 0.5-log reduction in titer by the end of the period (Figs 10, 11).

For vB_EcoP_ZR1, storage at room temperature resulted in a rapid 1-log reduction within the first week. The titer remained stable until week 6, followed by a further 2.5-log reduction between weeks 6 and 10, resulting in approximately a 4-log loss. At -20 °C, a 2-log reduction occurred within the first two weeks, followed by brief stabilization. However, by week 6, no viable phage particles were detectable. Storage at -60 °C resulted in a 1.5-log reduction after two weeks, with a gradual decline over time, culminating in an approximately 4-log total reduction by week 10.

Phage vB_EcoM_ZR2 followed a similar trend but showed slightly greater titer loss under some conditions (Fig. 11). At room temperature, a 2-log reduction occurred within the first week, with relative stability maintained until week 7. A subsequent 2-log drop occurred between weeks 7 and 10, leading to an overall ~4-log reduction. At -20 °C, a more pronounced 3-log reduction was observed within two weeks, with phage becoming undetectable by week 6. At -60 °C, a gradual decline resulted in a total ~3.5-log reduction over 10 weeks. Overall,

Figure 10. Long-term stability of phage vB_EcoP_ZR1 during storage over 10 weeks under different temperature conditions. Phage titers were determined at the indicated time points using the double-agar overlay assay and are expressed as \log_{10} PFU/mL. Storage conditions included room temperature (RT), 4 °C, -20 °C (frozen in 12.5% glycerol), and -60 °C (deep frozen in 50% glycerol). Values represent the mean of three independent measurements.

Figure 11. Long-term stability of phage vB_EcoM_ZR2 during storage over 10 weeks under different temperature conditions. Phage titers were determined at the indicated time points using the double-agar overlay assay and are expressed as \log_{10} PFU/mL. Storage conditions included room temperature (RT), 4 °C, -20 °C (frozen in 12.5% glycerol), and -60 °C (deep frozen in 50% glycerol). Values represent the mean of three independent measurements.

4 °C storage provided the best long-term stability for both phages, while -20 °C and room temperature resulted in significant loss of viability over time.

Discussion

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) poses a growing global threat, with projections indicating a substantial increase in mortality if effective alternatives to conventional antibiotics are not urgently pursued (Alvarez-Martinez et al. 2020). Among resistant pathogens, *E. coli* is particularly concerning due to its clinical prevalence and its ability to form biofilms, which contribute to persistent and treatment-refractory infections. While many *E. coli* strains are commensal, pathogenic variants such as extraintestinal pathogenic *E. coli* (ExPEC) are major contributors to infections in both humans and animals (Meena et al. 2023). The high prevalence of antibiotic-resistant *E. coli*, especially from poultry farming, and its zoonotic potential underscore the need for novel therapeutic strategies,

including bacteriophage (phage) therapy (Abdelrahman et al. 2022).

This study contributes to this need by isolating and characterizing two lytic phages, vB_EcoP_ZR1 and vB_EcoM_ZR2, from the contaminated Al-Zarqa River, a setting that likely promotes bacteriophage–bacteria co-evolution (Saadoun et al. 2021). Their preliminary phenotypic and morphological characterization reinforces the potential of environmental reservoirs as rich sources for therapeutic phages (Domingo-Calap and Delgado-Martinez 2018).

The target strains, *E. coli* (ATCC BAA-2452) and *E. coli* (ATCC 25922), were chosen to establish clinical relevance. ATCC BAA-2452 is an ESBL-producing strain, representing clinically significant antimicrobial resistance. On the other hand, the non-pathogenic ATCC 25922 is a well-established reference strain commonly used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing and phage characterization. The inclusion of an ESBL-producing strain also highlights the broader environmental and public health concern related to horizontal gene transfer and dissemination of resistance determinants (Liu et al. 2024a; Mandujano-Hernández et al. 2024; Zhang et al. 2025).

The isolated phages exhibited morphological and functional properties consistent with other *E. coli*-specific phages, with vB_EcoP_ZR1 showing *Podoviridae*-like morphology and vB_EcoM_ZR2 showing *Myoviridae*-like morphology. TEM supported their classification within the order *Caudovirales*, which contains many therapeutically relevant lytic phages (Turner et al. 2025). The observed halo surrounding vB_EcoM_ZR2 plaques may suggest the presence of depolymerase or other extracellular enzymes that could contribute to antibiofilm activity. However, this remains speculative, as no enzymatic assays or genomic analyses were performed to confirm depolymerase-related functions (Islam et al. 2024).

Although the burst sizes of vB_EcoP_ZR1 (5 PFU/cell) and vB_EcoM_ZR2 (9 PFU/cell) were near the lower end of historically reported ranges (10–1,000 PFU/cell) (Jin and Yin 2021), they remain within the range reported for other *E. coli* phages (Litt and Jaroni 2017; Yildirim et al. 2021; Li et al. 2022; Ren et al. 2025). Both phages yielded high-titer lysates, which are comparable to concentrations commonly used in experimental *in vivo* phage therapy studies (Shebs et al. 2019; Plumet et al. 2024). Phage vB_EcoM_ZR2, with a shorter latent period and larger plaques, may exhibit higher lytic efficiency under laboratory conditions than vB_EcoP_ZR1.

The host-range assays confirmed a narrow specificity for *E. coli*, consistent with most lytic phages. Notably, vB_EcoM_ZR2 exhibited activity against one clinical MDR *E. coli* isolate, supporting its relevance to current AMR challenges. Similar studies have reported lytic phages active against MDR avian pathogenic *E. coli* strains of zoonotic concern (Sattar et al. 2023) and antimicrobial-resistant diarrheagenic *E. coli* isolates (Sada and Tessema 2024). Interestingly, both phages produced lytic zones on some non-permissive strains that failed confirmation assays. This may reflect the activity of extracellular lytic agents,

such as phage-derived lysins, rather than classical phage replication (Cui et al. 2025; Panteleev et al. 2025).

The narrow host range observed for both phages, while advantageous for targeted therapy, may limit their standalone clinical applicability. This limitation can be addressed through the development of phage cocktails comprising multiple phages with complementary host ranges (Kortright et al. 2019; Melo et al. 2020). Such combinations not only broaden antibacterial coverage but also reduce the likelihood of resistance development by targeting bacterial populations through multiple infection mechanisms (Kakasis and Panitsa 2019). In addition, combining phages with antibiotics may further enhance antibacterial efficacy, expand host coverage, and help mitigate the emergence of resistant bacterial populations (Luscher et al. 2020).

A key finding of this study was the ability of both phages to inhibit biofilm formation and reduce pre-formed *E. coli* biofilms. These effects are likely driven by phage-mediated bacterial lysis and may also involve extracellular matrix-degrading enzymes such as depolymerases or lysins (Chang et al. 2022; Meneses et al. 2023; Maffei et al. 2024). Given the well-established role of biofilms in antibiotic tolerance and chronic infection persistence (Yin et al. 2019; Liu et al. 2024b), the observed antibiofilm activity supports the relevance of these phages for further development. Nevertheless, biofilm eradication remains challenging, and incomplete clearance is consistent with limitations in phage diffusion and replication within mature biofilm structures (Gordon and Ramirez 2024).

The relatively modest reduction in pre-formed biofilms (21–24%) may be attributed to the structural and physiological complexity of mature biofilms (Damyanova and Paunova-Krasteva 2025). The extracellular polymeric substance (EPS) matrix acts as a physical and chemical barrier that limits phage penetration and diffusion into deeper biofilm layers (Yin et al. 2019; Moryl et al. 2023). In addition, bacterial cells within mature biofilms often exhibit reduced metabolic activity or enter dormant states, which can impair phage replication efficiency (Yin et al. 2019; Liu et al. 2024b). These combined factors likely contribute to the partial, rather than complete, eradication of established biofilms (Husain et al. 2025).

Both phages demonstrated considerable pH tolerance, with vB_EcoP_ZR1 exhibiting superior acid resistance. These stability traits are desirable for therapeutic development, as they suggest survivability under acidic gastrointestinal conditions and during handling or formulation processes (Ranveer et al. 2024; Wei and Zhou 2024). Such robustness is consistent with recent findings emphasizing that stability under environmental conditions is an important factor for effective phage performance *in vivo* and in complex matrices such as food systems (Liu et al. 2024c).

Storage at 4 °C proved optimal for maintaining phage viability, consistent with extensive literature highlighting the vulnerability of many phage virions to temperature extremes (Cui et al. 2024; Huang et al. 2025). In contrast, cryopreservation at –20 °C and –60 °C resulted in noticeable titer reductions, particularly during the initial storage

period, despite the use of glycerol as a cryoprotectant. This decline aligns with prior reports attributing phage instability to ice crystal formation and solute concentration effects, especially when protective excipients are not optimized (Kim et al. 2024). While 4 °C storage remains a practical approach for short- to medium-term liquid preservation, these results highlight the need for improved formulation strategies. Approaches such as lyophilization or optimized stabilizing excipients may enhance long-term shelf life for therapeutic applications (Flint et al. 2023; Kim et al. 2024).

Overall, the strong *in vitro* lytic activity, stability profile, and antibiofilm effects observed in this study support the potential of these phages as candidates for further development against biofilm-associated *E. coli* infections (Gordillo Altamirano and Barr 2019; Chang et al. 2022). Although the phenotypic characteristics, such as clear plaque morphology and rapid lysis, are consistent with a lytic lifestyle, definitive confirmation of their strictly lytic nature requires whole-genome sequencing (Cui et al. 2024; Turner et al. 2025). Such analysis is essential to exclude lysogeny-associated genes, as well as virulence factors and antibiotic resistance determinants, thereby ensuring their safety for potential therapeutic applications (Nale and Clokie 2021; Cui et al. 2024). Furthermore, genomic characterization remains the most reliable approach to identify cryptic or “stealth” prophage elements that may not be evident from phenotypic observations alone (Turner et al. 2025).

Conclusion

This work identifies two river-derived bacteriophages with promising activity against *E. coli*, including strong antibiofilm effects and stability under varying pH and temperature conditions. Their narrow host specificity and strong *in vitro* performance highlight their potential as targeted antimicrobial agents. Future work will prioritize whole-genome sequencing to confirm the absence of undesirable genetic elements and to enable accurate taxonomic classification, which is a critical prerequisite for clinical development.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the Deanship of Research at Jordan University of Science and Technology for funding this research (Grant No. 20240124).

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors’ representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

Regarding the use of AI in the preparation of this manuscript, the authors declare the following: AI-assisted tools were used to improve English language quality, including grammar correction and paraphrasing, and to enhance clarity and readability in the Discussion and Conclusion sections. All scientific content, experimental design, data interpretation, and final manuscript decisions were made by the authors, who take full responsibility for the accuracy and integrity of the work.

Funding

This research was funded by the Deanship of Research, Jordan University of Science and Technology (Grant No. 20240124).

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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